

Author	Recaido, Ralph Josh DG.
Title	Developing a Performance Assessment Methodology to Measure the Integration of Environmental Sustainability in R&D: The Case of Food Manufacturing Companies in the Philippines
Year	2024
Program	Master in Research and Development Management

ABSTRACT

Food manufacturing companies hold a crucial position in advancing environmental sustainability through their corporate social responsibility and operational strategies. Efforts to integrate sustainability into daily operations are emerging as a strategic priority, especially for food companies and their R&D teams that operate in the Philippines. This study explores how R&D/PD functions in Philippine food companies incorporate environmental sustainability into their product development processes and proposes a standardized performance assessment procedure to evaluate these efforts. Using the Delphi method, insights from 10 R&D Managers from foodservice, FMCG/CPG, raw materials, and manufacturing companies identified four key stages of the R&D/PD process: Conceptualization, Development, Planning, and Commercialization. Each stage was found to require specific competencies and outputs. Using Soares' et al. (2024) list of environmental sustainability practices in project management, practices were prioritized and weighted using a Likert scale to develop a scoring system. A descriptive performance rubric was integrated to evaluate R&D personnel and projects. By virtue of universal consensus amongst all the panelists, an overall performance assessment tool was developed.

The results highlight that while environmental sustainability practices are recognized as foundational requirements within R&D/PD projects, a structured performance assessment framework enables R&D/PD managers to quantify and drive sustainability efforts effectively across the whole process. This framework provides an actionable tool to foster green innovation, improve decision-making, and align R&D strategies with organizational and global sustainability goals in the food industry.

Keywords: Environmental sustainability, R&D Process, Performance assessment framework, Delphi method